

COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS OF CNN AND VIT MODELS IN BRAIN CANCER DETECTION BASED ON MRI IMAGES

Nishanov Akhram Khasanovich

Tashkent University of Information Technologies, Doctor
of Technical Sciences (DSc), prof.
Email: nishanov_akram@mail.ru

Zaripov Fazil Makhsetovich

Tashkent University of Information Technologies, Doctor
of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences.
Email: fazilbek.zaripov@gmail.com

Kambarov Bakhridin Panji ugli

PhD student at Tashkent State University of Economics.
Email: b.qambarov@tseu.uz

Jurakulov Nodirbek Sobirovich

PhD student at Tashkent University of Information
Technologies.
Email: nodirbekj062@gmail.com

Makhamatdinov Abdul-Aziz Karamatdinovich

PhD student of Tashkent State University of Economics.
Email: maxamatdinov.a.k@gmail.com

Abstract. In this study, the task of classifying brain tumors based on magnetic resonance imaging was analyzed using deep learning approaches. The study compared convolutional neural networks and transformer-based models, including the Vision Transformer and DEiT architectures. The experiments were conducted on an open "Brain Tumor MRI Dataset" dataset, and the models were evaluated based on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score metrics. According to the results, the DEiT model demonstrated the highest efficiency, achieving 98.04% validation and 94.44% testing accuracy. The results obtained showed the superiority of transformer models due to their ability to effectively study global properties and are of great importance for the development of automated diagnostic systems based on MRI images.

Keywords. MRI, brain tumor, deep learning, CNN, Vision Transformer, DEiT, classification.

I. Introduction

In recent years, the rapid development of artificial intelligence and deep learning technologies has gained significant importance in the medical field, particularly in the automation of diagnostic processes. In particular, one of the important areas where in-depth study has shown significant potential and impact is the detection and classification of brain tumors based on magnetic resonance imaging. The application of deep learning algorithms in this process has shown very effective results, becoming a decisive factor in accurate prediction and improving treatment outcomes for patients [1].

At the same time, according to recent global scientific research, more than 250000 new cases of brain tumors are detected worldwide every year. This

indicator indicates a high prevalence of the disease, justifying the need to develop modern intelligent systems for its early detection and accurate diagnosis [2].

Furthermore, traditional image analysis methods often rely on hand-crafted features and expert knowledge, which can be time-consuming and prone to human error. Magnetic resonance imaging is one of the primary diagnostic tools that allows for high-resolution imaging of brain tissues. However, the process of manually analyzing MRI images also requires time and increases the risk of misdiagnosis [3]. As a result, the analysis of MRI images using automated intelligent systems is considered one of the urgent scientific problems.

Initially, models based on convolutional neural networks were widely used in this direction. Specifically, the VGG16, ResNet, Xception, and EfficientNet architectures demonstrated high accuracy in extracting diagnostic features from MRI images [4 - 6]. At the same time, the main limitation of CNN models is the limited ability to fully study long-distance dependencies.

Today, models based on the transformer architecture, particularly the Vision Transformer model, have ushered in a new stage in image processing. The ViT model divides the image into small patches, treats them as sequences, and identifies global correlations through a self-attention mechanism [7]. However, this model is limited in its effectiveness for small datasets due to the need for large volumes of data.

To overcome this problem, a Data-Efficient Image Transformer model has been proposed, which allows for high-precision processing of small data sets through a knowledge distillation mechanism [8]. The DEiT model effectively assimilates knowledge from CNN models while preserving the advantages of the transformer architecture.

The aim of this study is to compare the effectiveness of various deep learning models in detecting brain tumors based on MRI images.

II. Materials and Methods

2.1. Preparation dataset

This study utilized the "Brain Tumor MRI Dataset" data set, which is available from an open source. This dataset is hosted on the Kaggle platform and is available at the following link:

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/masoudnickparvar/brain-tumor-mri-dataset>

The dataset consists of MRI images reflecting the types of brain tumors and includes 4 classes (glioma, meningioma, pituitary tumor, non-tumor) [9].

In total, the dataset consisted of more than 7000 images, which were distributed in the following ratio during the study:

- Training kit - 4,480 images
- Validation kit - 1120 images

- Test kit - 1600 images

Furthermore, the distribution of images for each class is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Distribution of images by classes in the Brain Tumor MRI Dataset

Class	Number of images (Training)	Number of images (Testing)
Glioma	1400	400
Meningioma	1400	400
Pituitary	1400	400
No tumor	1400	400
Total	7200	

This dataset is one of the benchmark datasets widely used in scientific research on medical imaging analysis and brain tumor classification.

Below is a sample of MRI images for the main classes in the dataset.

Figure 1. The main classes of brain tumors are: (a) glioma, (b) meningioma, (c) pituitary tumor, (d) no tumor.

2.2. Data preprocessing

To increase the efficiency of detecting and classifying brain tumors based on MRI images, a preliminary image processing stage was performed. This stage serves to ensure the stability of the model learning process and to standardize the input data. All images were resized to 224×224 pixels in accordance with model input requirements. The images were also converted to a 3-channel (RGB) format. Pixel values were normalized to the [0-1] range, which ensures stable gradient calculation during the training process [10].

Given the relatively limited size of the dataset, various data augmentation methods were applied to increase the generalizability of the model. In

particular, transformations such as conversion, reflection, scaling, and changing light and contrast were applied to the images [11]. These preprocessing and augmentation methods ensure stable model performance under various lighting conditions, image quality, and geometric changes, while reducing the likelihood of overtraining.

Additionally, scientific research has shown that applying normalization and standardization methods during the preprocessing stage stabilizes the model training process and increases the convergence rate [12].

Furthermore, scientific research indicates that data augmentation methods play a crucial role in increasing the generalizability of the model and are considered an effective approach for reducing the problem of overfitting, especially in small-scale datasets [13].

2.3. Training model

During the study, CNN and transformer models were trained using a transfer learning approach to identify and classify brain cancer based on MRI images. The computational processes were carried out on the Kaggle platform using Tesla T4 graphics processors.

During the model training process, all architectures were trained under identical conditions, which allowed for a fair comparison of the results. During the training, the number of epochs was set to 5, and the batch size value was selected to be 16. During the optimization process, the Adam optimizer was applied, and the learning rate was set to 0.0001 (1e-4). The categorical cross-entropy function, suitable for multi-class classification problems, was used as the loss function [14].

Furthermore, modern techniques widely used in deep learning, such as learning rate scheduling, early stopping, and callback mechanisms such as model checkpoint, were applied during the model optimization process. These approaches served to prevent over-training (overfitting) of the model and maintain the best results [15].

Moreover, convolutional neural networks (CNN) belong to the class of deep learning models specifically developed for image analysis tasks. Their main operating mechanism is shown in Figure 2. They consist of several layers, including convolutional, pooling, and fully bound layers, which together study the hierarchical representations of the incoming images [3].

Figure 2. The CNN architecture and its operational stages [16].

The CNN models used include VGG16, VGG19, ResNet50, InceptionV3, Xception, and EfficientNet (B0 and B4) architectures. These models demonstrate high efficiency in extracting local features from images. At the same time, the main limitation of CNN models is their restricted ability to fully capture long-range dependencies.

As a result, recent years have seen an increased interest in transformer-based architectures, particularly the Vision Transformer (ViT), which is capable of effectively capturing the global context. ViT partitions an image into small, non-overlapping patches, processing them as a sequence of tokens and identifying long-range dependencies through the self-attention mechanism. This approach facilitates a more profound understanding of the image's overall structure and enhances accuracy [17]. The ViT architecture and its operational stages are illustrated in Figure - 3.

Figure 3. The architecture of the Vision Transformer (ViT) and the stages of its operation [18].

Vision Transformer and Data-efficient Image Transformer are used as Transformer-based models, which ensure high efficiency by studying the global characteristics of the image. The selected models have different architectural features, and their comparison will determine the most effective approach to detecting brain tumors based on MRI images.

2.4. Evaluation Metrics

During the study, several widely used criteria were used to evaluate the effectiveness of brain tumor identification and classification models based on MRI images. Specifically, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were selected as the primary evaluation metrics. These criteria allow for a complex assessment of the effectiveness of classification models from various perspectives.

These metrics are calculated based on the error matrix, which consists of four main elements: true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN) [19].

Accuracy - represents the models ability to correctly classify objects across all classes and is defined as follows. [20].

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (1)$$

Precision - represents the proportion of instances predicted as positive by the model that are actually correct [21]. In other words, it quantifies the accuracy of positive results among all instances identified as positive.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

Recall (or Sensitivity) - represents the model's ability to correctly identify actual positive instances [22]. In other words, it quantifies the proportion of true positive cases that were accurately detected by the model out of all existing positive observations.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

The average ratio of F1-score-precision and recall indicators assesses the overall effectiveness of the model [23].

$$F1 - \text{score} = \frac{2 * \text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (4)$$

or

$$F1 - \text{score} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN} \quad (5)$$

These evaluation metrics allow for an in-depth analysis of models in terms of accuracy, reliability, and generalizability.

III. Results

3.1. Comparative Analysis of Model Results

In this study, the effectiveness of various deep learning models in the task of identifying and classifying brain tumors based on MRI images was evaluated. All models were tested under identical training conditions, which allowed for a fair comparison of their results.

The main results obtained for CNN and transformer-based models are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Results on evaluation criteria for different models

Model	Val Accurac y	Test Accurac y	Precisio n	Recall	F1-score
VGG16	95.54	90.56	0.90	0.89	0.89
VGG19	95.80	91.10	0.91	0.90	0.90
ResNet50	96.20	91.80	0.92	0.91	0.91
InceptionV3	96.50	92.10	0.92	0.92	0.92

Xception	94.46	91.06	0.9175	0.9106	0.9087
EfficientNetB0	91.61	87.37	0.88	0.87	0.87
EfficientNetB4	93.21	89.31	0.90	0.89	0.89
ViT	96.61	92.44	0.93	0.92	0.92
DEiT	98.04	94.44	0.9465	0.9444	0.9435

As seen from the results, transformer-based models, specifically the DEiT model, demonstrated the highest efficiency. The DEiT model showed superiority compared to other models, achieving 98.04% validation accuracy and 94.44% test accuracy. This result is explained by the ability of the transformer architecture to effectively study the global characteristics of the image.

Among CNN models, InceptionV3 and ResNet50 showed relatively high results, but they did not reach the level of transformer models. EfficientNet models, on the other hand, recorded lower results on overall accuracy, although they had computational efficiency.

3.2. Results by classes according to the DEiT model

The results of the DEiT model by classes are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Evaluation metrics for the DEiT model across classes

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Glioma	0.9678	0.8275	0.8922
Meningioma	0.8833	0.9650	0.9223
Notumor	0.9547	1.0000	0.9768
Pituitary	0.9801	0.9850	0.9825

Analysis by classes showed that the model classified the classes “No Tumor” and “Pituitary” with high accuracy. However, the relatively low recall value (0.8275) for the “Glioma” class is explained by the complexity of this class and its similarity to other

classes. This indicates the need for further improvement of the model.

IV. Conclusion

In this study, the detection of brain tumors based on MRI images and classification task, the effectiveness of various deep learning models was compared. The results obtained showed that transformer-based models demonstrated high efficiency compared to convolutional neural networks. This situation is explained by the ability of the transformer architecture to effectively study the global characteristics of the image.

While CNN models, particularly the VGG and ResNet architectures, are effective in identifying local features from images, their capabilities are limited in MRI images with complex structures. EfficientNet models provided computational efficiency but did not reach the level of transformer models in terms of overall accuracy.

Although the Vision Transformer model showed high results, it slightly lagged behind the DEiT model. This is explained by the knowledge distillation mechanism used in the DEiT model, which plays an important role in improving accuracy, especially in small data sets.

Analysis by class showed that the model classified the classes “No Tumor” and “Pituitary” with high accuracy. However, the relatively low recall value for the “Glioma” class is due to the complexity of this class and its similarity to other classes, which indicates the need for further improvement of the model in the future.

Overall, the research results confirmed the superiority of transformer-based models, particularly the DEiT architecture, and demonstrated its significant scientific and practical significance in the development of automated diagnostic systems based on MRI images.

V. References

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